

Study Title: High Risk Prevention Programme
**Behaviour change in action – Pilot implementation project in
general practice**

The High-risk prevention programme is led by the:

- Irish Heart Foundation (IHF)

And is in partnership with the:

- Health Services Executive (HSE) who are jointly funding this project.
- University College Dublin (UCD) who provided ethical approval for this study.

Before you decide whether you wish to take part, you should read the information provided below carefully and feel free to contact us with any questions.

Principal investigators: Dr Walter Cullen (UCD School of Medicine)
Tim Collins (Irish Heart Foundation)
Janis Morrissey (Irish Heart Foundation)

Why should I take part and in this research?

By taking part:

- You will get the chance to improve your health in relation to lifestyle choices and habits that may affect your risk of heart disease and stroke.
- You will help us see if the ‘High Risk Preventive Programme’ is effective and learn how we can have the best impact on people in the community who are at risk of heart disease and stroke.
- You will help us and inform national policy concerning management, prevention, and treatment of cardiovascular disease in Irish communities.

Information

If you need any further information now or at any time in the future, please contact:

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Feidhmeannacht na Seirbhíse Sláinte
Health Service Executive

What is this research about and why have you been invited?

Prevention of heart disease and stroke in high-risk communities like yours is a very important issue to us. This program is aimed for people who are at high risk of developing heart disease. We wish to improve individuals in the community's knowledge and skills to improve their health behaviours around the controllable risk factors to heart disease and stroke.

You are being asked to participate because you are a patient at one of this study's participating general practices based in a community who are shown to be at higher risk of heart disease and stroke. The intervention will be carried out through the 'Your Heart' wellbeing programme in your general practice. In taking part:

- You will receive 6 weeks of one-to-one help from a health expert.
- You will be given the option to join a private Facebook group led by Irish heart foundation, providing information and tips about improving your health.
- You will receive follow up support calls 3, 6 and 9 months after the first 6 weeks.

Examples of information and supports provided include but is not limited to;

Blood Pressure	Cholesterol
Healthy eating	Being more active
Weight management	Stress
Quitting smoking	

What are the risks of taking part in this research study?

There is no risk of physical harm associated with taking part in this research study. However, it is possible that the questionnaire/interview may identify a health-related issues that requires you to seek advice from your doctor. If this happens please speak to a member of staff at the general practice you are attending as part of this study if you would like further guidance on whom to consult.

How will you find out what happens with this project?

If you wish to learn the outcomes of this project, the researcher will take your contact details and send you a summary at the conclusion of the project.

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What will happen if you agree to taking part in this research study?

If you agree to take part in this research, we will agree a time and place that suits you to meet/ phone so that questionnaires/interviews can be conducted.

The study questionnaire will involve some routine physical health assessments carried out by a health professional. These will include but are not limited to topics such as:

- Alcohol consumption
- Stress and mental Wellbeing
- Food and Nutrition
- Physical activity levels

You will have certain health checks or measurements taken by a health professional before and after you take part in the study. These will help inform any positive changes on your health throughout the study length. These will include:

- Resting heart rate,
- Blood pressure
- Cholesterol
- Body Mass Index (BMI)
- Waist measurement
- Health history questionnaire. Such as family history and any illnesses, you may suffer from.
- Blood Glucose levels

Can you change your mind at any stage if you do not want to take part anymore?

- You do not have to take part in this study.
- You can change your mind about taking part in the study any time you like.
- You do not have to give us a reason.

Your Privacy?

In terms of your information

- All your information will be anonymised and so it will not be possible to identify you or your information data.
- All your information will be collected and stored securely.
- You can review, amend, or remove your data at any stage up until the data analysis phase.
- Research will be conducted with UCD who will only receive anonymised data and will be used evaluate how successful the programme has been.
- Your information will be destroyed by UCD after an appropriate retention period.

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I have read and understood the Information Leaflet about this research project. The information has been fully explained to me and I have been able to ask questions, all of which have been answered to my satisfaction.	Yes	No
I understand that I don't have to take part in this study and that I can opt out at any time. I understand that I don't have to give a reason for opting out and I understand that opting out won't affect my future medical care.	Yes	No
I am aware of the potential risks of this research study.	Yes	No
I have been given a copy of the Information Leaflet and this completed consent form for my records.	Yes	No
Storage and future use of information: I give my permission for information I provide, to be stored or electronically processed. By doing so I consent to this information being used in <u>related or other studies in the future</u> . Further, I understand that studies of this nature will need to receive their own ethical approvals and that my data will also be anonymous in these studies.	Yes	No
I agree to take part in the above research study.	Yes	No
I agree to participating in the High Risk Prevention Pilot with the Irish Heart Foundation and my GP practice I consent to my GP to share my pre and post programme health measurements relevant to the programme the Irish Heart Foundation team for this purpose.	Yes	No
Participants Name (Block Capitals)		
Participants Signature		
Address:		
Phone:	Date:	

To be completed by GP practice staff.

I the undersigned, have taken the time to fully explain to the above patient the nature and purpose of this pilot study.

Name (Block Capitals): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____